

Dynamic edge-to-cloud model selection via confidence estimation

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Abstract—Following the recent success of large language models (LLMs) in enabling novel artificial intelligence (AI) services such as ChatGPT, there has been a growing interest in adapting LLMs to run on edge devices [1]. However, running state-of-the-art LLMs on today’s resource-limited edge devices is challenging at best, and in many cases impossible. Resource requirements of LLMs can be reduced by opting to use smaller models (i.e., fewer parameters) and through simplifying optimization techniques (e.g., [2]), although such concessions invariably result in some amount of LLM response quality degradation [1]. In prior work [3], we demonstrated how simple confidence models can be designed to detect incorrect LLM-generated responses to yes-or-no questions. To mitigate losses in response quality when adapting LLMs to run on edge devices, we explore with a hybrid approach in which an edge-based LLM is only trusted when confidence in its response is sufficiently high, otherwise the query is routed to a more complex cloud-based LLM. This allows computation to be opportunistically offloaded from cloud platforms to edge devices, improving average response times and reducing LLM execution costs without significantly sacrificing output quality. We test the approach on a question-answering dataset and report the observed tradeoffs between response accuracy and operating costs, as well as the reliability of our confidence models at detecting incorrect responses.

Keywords—confidence models, large language models, artificial intelligence, error detection, error correction

Despite the recent success of large language models (LLMs) in powering artificial intelligence (AI) services across a vast array of applications, their practical exclusivity to cloud platforms has limited their potential due to privacy, energy, and accessibility concerns [1]. One solution to addressing these concerns is to move LLMs to the edge, where they can be used without requiring users to hand off sensitive data, lifting the need for Internet connectivity, and potentially distributing their execution across more energy-efficient hardware [1]. However, the relatively limited resources available on today’s edge devices demands significant optimizations, such as reducing model complexity (i.e., fewer parameters) and streamlining execution (e.g., [2]), both of which almost assuredly come at the expense of model output quality [1].

One possible way to compensate for reduced model output quality is to detect “bad” outputs (e.g., generated text that is factually incorrect) so that they can be discarded, replaced, or otherwise prevented from causing problems in downstream processes. In prior work [3], we described how simple

Figure 1. A hybrid edge-to-cloud two-LLM system for question answering. The edge model is run first; if confidence is above a probability threshold τ , the LLM’s response is accepted. Otherwise, a more complex LLM on the cloud is used. A new confidence score is then computed for its response; the response is accepted if confidence is above the threshold, otherwise no response is accepted.

confidence models (hundreds of parameters) can be designed to predict the correctness of responses generated by LLMs (billions of parameters) for yes-or-no questions. We demonstrated that a set of uncertainty measures that are only weakly correlated with model output correctness can be combined to identify a subset of responses as correct with high confidence, i.e., with a probability of correctness that exceeds a desired threshold. Such responses are *trusted*, whereas those with sub-threshold confidence are not. If low confidence responses are ignored, the remaining set of trusted responses can be expected to have improved accuracy. Moreover, if the confidence estimates generated by the confidence model are sufficiently well calibrated [4], the overall accuracy of trusted responses will typically be above or at least equal to the chosen confidence threshold.

In this work, we explore the use of confidence as the decision axis for model selection in scenarios where two different models are available for use. Rather than simply discard low-confidence

responses, we instead defer their associated questions to an alternative model in the hope of generating a higher-confidence output. We implement this approach in the hybrid edge-cloud system visualized in Figure 1. The system contains two LLMs, one run on the edge (LLaMa-2 7B with activation-aware weight quantization [2]) and the other on the cloud (GPT 3.5). Two confidence models are trained, one for each LLM, to assign confidence estimates to their respective outputs. The edge-based LLM is assumed to be less accurate in answering questions than its cloud counterpart due to its significantly lower complexity that allows it to be run on commodity hardware. The objective is to run only the edge-based LLM whenever possible, only deferring to the cloud-based LLM when the former’s responses are assigned low confidence. If the edge-based LLM is both cheaper to run and capable of generating high-confidence responses, then the hybrid system should reduce overall cost without allowing response accuracy to fall below the specified confidence threshold.

We evaluate the hybrid system on the species occurrence dataset described in [3] and compare the observed performance (accuracy versus operating costs) of the hybrid system, the cloud-based LLM, and the edge-based LLM. The dataset consists of roughly 30,000 yes-or-no questions derived from the recorded occurrences of plant, animal, and fungi species as

served through the Integrated Digitized Biocollections (iDigBio) data portal (<https://idigbio.org>). While the subject matter of the dataset is not of specific importance to this work, we use an LLM’s performance on the dataset as a proxy for comparing the more general abilities of different LLMs at memorizing and recalling information.

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